

**Synthesis, growth and characterization of
R-Mandelic acid S-alanine hemihydrates single crystals**

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Abstract

Nonlinear optical (NLO) active single crystals of R-Mandelic acid S-alanine hemihydrate (RMSA) were grown by solvent evaporation procedure at 37°C. The lattice constants were determined by single crystal and powder X-ray diffraction analysis. RMSA crystallizes in triclinic structure. Transmission spectrum of RMSA shows the UV cut-off wavelength at 268 nm. The vibrations of functional groups were elucidated by FTIR spectroscopy. The molecular structure of RMSA was established by ¹³C-NMR spectroscopy. Kurtz–Perry SHG test showed positive results for SHG. The SHG efficiency is found to increase for RMSA when compared to pure alanine. Third order nonlinear optical study was carried out using single beam Z-scan technique using He-Ne laser. Closed aperture study reveals the positive nonlinearity in RMSA and open aperture study reveals the reverse saturation absorption of the grown crystal.